

1 **The role of extra-striate areas in conscious motor behavior: a**
2 **registered report with Fast-Optical Imaging**

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9

10 **Abstract**

11 Disclosing the brain areas responsible for the emergence of visual awareness and their timing of
12 activation represents one of the major challenges in consciousness research. In particular, isolating
13 the neural processes strictly related to consciousness from concurrent neural dynamics, either related
14 to prerequisites or post-perceptual processing, has long engaged consciousness research. In this
15 framework, the present study aims at unraveling the spatio-temporal dynamics underlying conscious
16 vision by adopting a distinctive experimental design in which both awareness and motor response are
17 manipulated, allowing the segregation of neural activity strictly related to awareness from response-
18 related mechanisms. To this end, we employed a GO/NOGO detection task, in which participants
19 responded or withhold responding according to the experimental condition. Critically, during the
20 performance of the task, participants' brain activity was recorded by means of Event-Related Optical
21 Signal (EROS) technique, which provides accurate information about brain functions both from the
22 temporal and spatial point of view within the covered regions, simultaneously. The combination of
23 this experimental design with EROS recording enabled us to pinpoint the neural correlates underlying
24 conscious vision and to disentangle them from processes related to the response. Results revealed that
25 extra-striate areas, specifically the Lateral Occipital Complex (LOC), showed greater awareness-
26 related activity independently of motor response. Our findings support the view that LOC plays a key
27 role as a proper correlate of visual awareness, rather than post-perceptual or response-related
28 processes. They also show that awareness modulates motor activity only when a response is executed,
29 clarifying how conscious perception influences downstream motor processing.

30 **1. Introduction**

31 Consciousness, namely the set of subjective experiences we have when we are awake, is one of the
32 most intriguing topics debated in neuroscience research. In particular, the search for its neural
33 correlates (NCC) has permeated the literature in recent decades. In broad strokes, one of the most
34 widely used approaches to assess such NCCs involves contrasting brain activity occurring when a
35 visual stimulus enters consciousness with brain activity occurring when the same stimulus does not
36 reach awareness. This renowned paradigm is known as *contrastive analysis* (Aru *et al.*, 2012) and
37 has been frequently combined with electrophysiological recording or functional neuroimaging,
38 leading to numerous and dissimilar results (Förster *et al.*, 2020). Indeed, the interpretations of spatio-
39 temporal dynamics underlying conscious vision are among the most disparate. ERP studies propose
40 two possible electrophysiological markers as correlates of visual awareness: an earlier occipito-
41 temporal negative deflection (i.e., Visual Awareness Negativity – VAN) detectable 200 ms after the
42 presentation of the stimulus, and a later positivity (i.e., Late Positivity – LP) widespread over centro-
43 parietal regions, peaking 300-500 ms after the stimulus onset (Koivisto & Revonsuo, 2010). However,
44 the electrophysiological signature/s characterizing conscious vision has still to be elucidated. This
45 may be attributed to one of the main limitations of the contrastive analysis, which is represented by
46 its ineffectiveness in dissociating the true NCC (i.e., the set of neural correlates necessary and
47 sufficient to enable consciousness) from concurrent neural dynamics either related to prerequisites or
48 post-perceptual processing (Aru *et al.*, 2012). In most prior studies aiming at identifying such NCCs,
49 participants were asked to make judgments about their experience. However, such an operation could
50 lead to confounding neural processes related to the task, not strictly to awareness per se.

51 For this reason, in an effort to disentangle the proper correlates of consciousness from neural activity
52 related to the response, no-report paradigms have been employed. In this framework, no-report
53 paradigms, where participants are not requested to perform any tasks or to provide any judgments
54 about their perceptual experience, represent an advantageous tool to dissociate the neural processes
55 strictly related to consciousness from subsequent processes related to the required response (Tsuchiya
56 *et al.*, 2015; Hatamimajoumerd *et al.*, 2022). Studies employing this kind of paradigm with different
57 techniques such as EEG and fMRI concluded that LP is highly modulated by several different
58 cognitive processes occurring at later stages of processing (Mazzi *et al.*, 2020; Schlossmacher *et al.*,
59 2020; Dembski *et al.*, 2021; Kronemer *et al.*, 2022), as well as by the task relevance of the stimulus
60 (Makeig & Jung, 2000; Pitts *et al.*, 2014; Shafto & Pitts, 2015; Schelonka *et al.*, 2017; Dellert *et al.*,
61 2021; Hense *et al.*, 2024). By contrast, the role of response requirements, as well as that of attention,
62 on the VAN are still debated as different studies have reported both positive (e.g., Bola &
63 Doradzińska, 2021; Dellert *et al.*, 2021; Doradzińska & Bola, 2024) and negative (e.g., Koivisto *et*

64 *al.*, 2006; Cohen *et al.*, 2020; Dellert *et al.*, 2022; Ciupińska *et al.*, 2024) results. Interestingly, in a
65 study published in 2016 by Koivisto and colleagues (Koivisto *et al.*, 2016), authors successfully
66 dissociated ERP correlates of visual awareness from those related to post-perceptual mechanisms,
67 disclosing that VAN was not modulated by response requirements. The authors adopted a particular
68 partial-report paradigm in which participants were sometimes asked to provide a report by pressing a
69 response button when they were aware of the stimulus and sometimes to withhold responding in case
70 of awareness. They found that, while the amplitude of LP was modulated by the response (i.e., it was
71 greater in trials where participants were asked to respond in case of awareness, compared to the Aware
72 condition where they were asked to withhold responding), VAN did not change depending on task
73 requirements. This allowed Koivisto and colleagues to advocate for an early onset of visual
74 awareness: the phenomenal content of a visual experience, indeed, takes place before LP, more
75 specifically in the temporal window of VAN.

76 Several pieces of evidence are consistent in considering VAN as the electrophysiological signature
77 of phenomenal consciousness (Koivisto *et al.*, 2008; Railo *et al.*, 2015), while the localization of its
78 neural generator still remains open. In this regard, previous MEG source localization studies (Vanni
79 *et al.*, 1996; Liu *et al.*, 2012) identified the Lateral Occipital Complex (LOC), an extra-striate visual
80 areas traditionally associated with objects recognition, as the generator of VAN. Moreover, previous
81 no-report studies using both EEG and fMRI (Dellert *et al.*, 2021; Kronemer *et al.*, 2022) have also
82 found awareness effects in LOC and linked it to VAN. The same result was achieved in a recent work
83 aimed at unravelling the spatio-temporal dynamics underlying conscious vision (Colombari *et al.*,
84 2024). In such study, participants were asked to perform a discrimination task on the orientation of a
85 tilted Gabor patch while their brain activity was recorded first with EEG and then with Fast Optical
86 Imaging. This allowed authors to identify the exact temporal window of VAN and LP and then, by
87 taking advantage of the peculiarity of Fast Optical Imaging of achieving both temporal and spatial
88 accurate information (Gratton & Corballis, 1995; Gratton & Fabiani, 2010; Baniqued *et al.*, 2013), to
89 investigate the spatio-temporal unfolding of brain activity occurring in these predetermined time
90 windows. Authors contrasted activity of Aware trials (i.e., trials in which participants reported to
91 perceive the orientation of the stimulus) with activity of Unaware ones and observed a sustained
92 activation of LOC in the VAN temporal window, consistently with the above-mentioned MEG
93 studies. More interestingly, they observed that, only when the stimulus crossed the threshold of
94 consciousness, activity in extra-striate visual areas triggered subsequent activation of motor areas,
95 although motor response was required in both Aware and Unaware conditions. Authors tried to
96 interpret this unexpected finding by ascribing it to the selection of the correct response, that could be
97 provided in the Aware trials only where participants consciously perceived the stimulus. Indeed, in

98 Aware trials participants had to press a specific button on the response box (to provide the correct
99 answer about the orientation of the Gabor patch), while when the stimulus was unseen (i.e., Unaware
100 trials) they had to respond randomly, by pressing indifferently one of the two response buttons.
101 However, the employed experimental paradigm did not allow the authors to thoroughly investigate
102 this issue. Thus, in order to clarify the interplay between extra-striate areas and motor regions in
103 awareness, in the present study we adopted a go/no-go detection task (similar to that adopted by
104 Koivisto *et al.*, 2016), while recording participants' brain activity by means of Fast Optical Imaging.
105 Specifically, Event-Related Optical Signal (EROS) technique was employed. This technique, by
106 shedding near-infrared light through the brain tissues, is able to detect changes in the light scattering
107 properties that are known to be directly related to neural activity, thus providing simultaneous spatial
108 resolution at the sub-centimeter level and temporal resolution below 100 ms within the cortical
109 regions accessible to near-infrared light, that is, cortical structures no deeper than approximately
110 3 cm from the scalp surface (Gratton *et al.*, 1997; Gratton & Fabiani, 1998, 2001). The main
111 limitations of the technique are its restricted depth of penetration, which precludes imaging of
112 deep cortical structures and subcortical regions, and its relatively low signal-to-noise ratio, which
113 requires a large number of trials per condition (Gratton & Fabiani, 2010). Accordingly, the
114 montage employed here was designed to provide dense coverage of the occipital, temporal, and
115 parietal cortices relevant to the pre-specified ROIs, and does not extend to prefrontal cortex (see
116 Figure 2 and Section 2.6). Critically, the study adopted a distinctive paradigm manipulating both
117 awareness and response. The latter, indeed, was provided sometimes in the Aware condition
118 (condition Aware-GO/Unaware-NOGO) and sometimes in the Unaware one (condition Aware-
119 NOGO/Unaware-GO). This double manipulation enabled us to unravel the spatio-temporal unfolding
120 of awareness-related activity, by disentangling neural activity related to awareness from response-
121 related mechanisms. Indeed, in the present study, we could investigate the NCCs both when the motor
122 response was required and when no task was performed, thus allowing to isolate consciousness effects
123 from the effects related to the task. Importantly, the experimental paradigm adopted enabled us to
124 elucidate the interplay between extra-striate visual areas and motor areas. Indeed, in addition to
125 conventional EROS analyses, we performed Granger Causality analysis, in order to disclose the
126 relationship existing among the investigated areas. In broad strokes, Granger analysis allows to move
127 beyond the classical identification of cortical activation provided by EROS analysis by disclosing
128 functional circuits underpinning the investigated brain function (Seth *et al.*, 2015). When coupled
129 with EROS, Granger Causality analysis represents a powerful tool to highlight predictive relationship
130 between activations in the investigated regions of interest (ROI) at different time-points (Parisi *et al.*,
131 2020).

132 Based on previous literature suggesting that VAN is independent from subjective report (Koivisto *et*
133 *al.*, 2016; Ye *et al.*, 2024) and LOC represents the cortical generator of VAN (Liu *et al.*, 2012;
134 Colombari *et al.*, 2024), we expected Aware trials to elicit early greater activation of LOC,
135 independently of the response requirement. Moreover, by combining EROS conventional analysis
136 with Granger Causality analysis, and manipulating both awareness and motor response, we aimed to
137 highlight potential interplay between consciousness-related extra-striate areas and response-related
138 motor areas both when the motor response was required and when it had to be inhibited.

139 **2. Methods**

140 This manuscript corresponds to Stage 2 of a Registered Report. The Stage 1 protocol has been peer-
141 reviewed and is available at <https://osf.io/8ya2t>.

142 **2.1 Ethics Information**

143 The study was approved by the local Ethics Committee (Prog.171CESC) and it was conducted in
144 accordance with the principles laid down in the 2013 Declaration of Helsinki. Participants were
145 recruited from the University of Verona community, by means of printed flyers displayed on notice
146 boards at different University of Verona sites and through advertisements on social media. Each
147 participant was fully informed about the modalities of the study before taking part in the experiment
148 and written informed consent was signed. In addition, participants received compensation for their
149 participation and were debriefed after the conclusion of the experiment.

150 **2.2 Participants**

151 We recruited healthy adults, right-handed (as assessed by means of the standard handedness inventory
152 *Edinburgh Handedness Questionnaire*; Oldfield, 1971) and aged between 18 and 50 years old. All of
153 them had to report normal or corrected-to-normal vision, no history of neurological or psychiatric
154 disorders and no contraindications to MRI. The study was conducted at the Panda lab of the
155 University of Verona (Italy).

156 *2.2.1 Sample size estimation*

157 The estimate of the sample size for the current study is based on our previous EROS study (Colombari
158 *et al.*, 2024), in which a similar paradigm was adopted, and similar analyses on similar ROIs were
159 performed. Specifically, EROS data from the ROI of LOC were extracted, and significant time-points
160 were averaged within participants so to have one value for each of them. Then, a one-sample t-test
161 was performed ($t(23) = 2.99$, $p = .006$, Cohen's $d = .611$), and the resulting Cohen's d was employed
162 to compute the sample size estimation for the current study. Specifically, the estimated sample size

163 for research questions Q1 (i.e., “Can we replicate Colombari et al., 2024 findings showing that LOC
164 is an NCC?”) and Q2 (i.e., “Is the activity in LOC independent from the response?”) was calculated
165 with G-Power software (v. 3.1.9.7), with a power of 90% and a level of significance of 2%. The
166 estimated sample size resulted in 32 participants (critical $t = 2.143$; actual power = 0.900). Considering
167 that the estimated sample size for this study ($n = 32$) is more than double the typical sample size of
168 EROS studies present in literature, the same estimated sample size seems to be also adequate to
169 answer research questions Q3 (i.e., “Does consciousness modulate the activation of motor areas in a
170 detection task?”) and Q4 (i.e., “Does consciousness modulate the activation of motor areas in
171 ABSENCE of motor response?”). For a review of the existing EROS literature, see Supplementary
172 Table 1 at https://osf.io/ebfu3/?view_only=9ec2e6bf32ba4a8bb8b858639ec40a59) from which
173 emerges that, on average, EROS studies employ experimental samples composed of about 13
174 participants (mean 12.944; SD 7.008).

175 *2.2.2 Exclusion Criteria*

176 As better specified in section 2.4, before getting involved in the study, participants underwent a
177 perceptual threshold assessment, in order to identify the proper stimulus to be employed in the main
178 experiment. To be enrolled in the study, participants had to successfully complete this session. The
179 criterion used was that one of the stimuli presented during the threshold assessment had to be
180 acknowledged as perceived by a minimum of 25%, a maximum of 75%, or closest to the 50% of the
181 times (i.e., at perceptual threshold level). If no stimulus resulted at the threshold level, the
182 participant was not enrolled in the study.

183 In addition, participants who did not complete all the experimental sessions, as well as participants
184 reporting a level of Awareness superior to 75% or inferior to 25% at the end of the experiment were
185 excluded from analyses. This was to maintain comparable the number of trials in the two
186 experimental conditions (i.e., Aware and Unaware) and to ensure a reliable EROS activity (because
187 of its relatively low signal-to-noise ratio, EROS needs a high number of trials per condition, in
188 order to compute statistics). Moreover, participants whose behavioral performance was affected by
189 biases related to the behavioral response (as assessed by catch trial analysis, explained more in
190 detail below) were excluded from the analyses (see below –*Section 2.8.1 Behavioral data* for more
191 detailed information on the analysis of catch trials). Finally, participants whose EROS signal could
192 not be detected properly during the experiment (for example because of too dark hair or technical
193 issues) were also not included in the analyses as well. In particular, the opacity value (i.e., the
194 product of the scattering and absorption coefficients) was estimated for each participant. Based on
195 this value, it was possible to judge the quality of the signal for each participant, independently from
196 the experimental condition. Opacity values of all participants were averaged together providing the

197 absorption coefficient to be used when running statistical analysis. Participants whose opacity value
198 was equal to 0 or exceeded three standard deviations of the mean were excluded from statistical
199 analyses.

200 Importantly, each participant who was excluded due to the previously mentioned exclusion criteria,
201 was replaced with the recruitment of another participant. Thus, the number of participants to be
202 recruited was increased to reach a total of 32 analyzed subjects, as specified in section 2.2.1.

203 **2.3 Stimuli**

204 Stimuli were created by means of a custom-made Matlab script (version R2022b; the MathWorks,
205 Inc., Natick, MA) and resized by means of Photoshop (Adobe Photoshop CC, v2014.0.0). As shown
206 in Figure 1, they were gray circles (.85 .85 .85 RGB), presented on a black background, with 8 radii
207 equally distanced from one another. One radius (the first one, clockwise) could be slightly thicker
208 than the others (critical trials) or not (catch trials). The thickness of the radius for critical stimuli was
209 individually assessed for each participant on the basis of a subjective perceptual threshold assessment
210 that was held before the main experiment.

211 Both in the perceptual threshold assessment and in the main experiment, the stimulus was presented
212 in the lower right quadrant of the screen, specifically at an eccentricity of 3.5° from the fixation cross
213 along the vertical meridian and of 2° along the horizontal one. This was to allow a left-lateralized
214 EROS montage, as a full-head montage is not achievable in our lab due to technical constraints (i.e.,
215 insufficient probes). Moreover, since EROS technique is sensitive to depth, a right-lateralized
216 stimulus ensures that it elicits activity in the left portion of the primary visual cortex, which is known
217 to be anatomically closer to the skull compared to the right one (Zhao *et al.*, 2022), thus ensuring a
218 better penetration of near-infrared light through brain tissues.

219 **2.4 Perceptual Threshold Assessment**

220 Before starting the experiment, participants underwent a perceptual threshold assessment, with the
221 aim of identifying, for each participant, the level of thickness of the critical radius so that it resulted
222 to be perceived as thicker 50% of the times. To this aim, stimuli with different levels of radius
223 thickness were randomly presented and the subjective perceptual threshold was measured using the
224 method of constant stimuli. Specifically, 9 levels of radius thickness were presented. The range of
225 stimuli to be used in the perceptual threshold assessment was selected based on the results of a pilot
226 experiment in which participants were asked to perform the same task employed in the perceptual
227 threshold assessment while presented with a wider range of radius thickness. This allowed us to
228 identify a smaller range of optimal stimuli to be presented thus excluding a range of stimuli whose

229 thickness was almost never or always reported by participants. Each level of radius thickness was
230 presented 5 times per block, for a total of 8 blocks. Thus, all the stimuli, as well as the catch stimulus,
231 were presented 40 times each. Participants were asked to press the spacebar as soon as they detected
232 the stimulus with a thicker radius. The stimulus identified as perceived a minimum of 25%, a
233 maximum of 75%, and closest to 50% of the times at the end of the subjective perceptual threshold
234 assessment was used in the experimental task, together with the catch. The perceptual threshold
235 assessment, as well as the main experiment, was conducted in a dimly illuminated room and
236 participants were sitting in front of a 17 in. LCD monitor (resolution 1920x1080, refresh rate of 144
237 Hz) placed at a viewing distance of 57 cm. Their head was held in place by means of an adaptable
238 chin rest so that eyes were aligned with the center of the screen. Both the perceptual threshold
239 assessment and the main experiment were programmed and administered using E-Prime 3.0 software
240 (E-Prime Psychology Software Tools Inc., Pittsburgh, PA, USA). Before starting the perceptual
241 threshold assessment, participants underwent a fixation training (Leung *et al.*, 2009), in order to
242 ensure they could maintain their gaze on the central fixation cross correctly.

243 **2.5 Experimental Procedure**

244 The experiment was composed of two identical sessions lasting approximately 3 hours each
245 performed on different days. The first session was preceded by the assessment of the subjective
246 perceptual threshold, which, in turn, lasted around 20 minutes. The two experimental sessions were
247 identical except for the EROS montages, specifically devised to obtain better coverage of the brain
248 areas of interest. The order of the montages was counterbalanced across participants, as well as the
249 order of conditions (see below for more detailed information).

250 The task was a two-conditions go/no-go detection task, similar to that adopted by Koivisto *et al.*,
251 2016, in which participants have to respond in different ways according to the experimental condition
252 (Table 1). In condition “Aware-GO”, they were asked to press the spacebar on the keyboard as soon
253 as they perceived the thicker radius, and withhold responding when they did not perceive any
254 difference among radii. On the contrary, in condition “Aware-NOGO”, participants were asked to
255 withhold responding when they perceived a thicker radius, and press the response button when they
256 did not perceive any difference. Each trial began with the presentation of a central fixation cross,
257 followed 500 ms later by a sound (1000Hz) presented for 100 ms, notifying participants of the
258 subsequent onset of the stimulus. After a random interval ranging from 500 to 600 ms, the stimulus
259 was presented for 100 ms in the lower right quadrant of the screen. After that, participants were asked
260 to respond according to the experimental condition. Each experimental session was composed of 24
261 blocks: 12 blocks for condition Aware-GO/Unaware-NOGO and 12 blocks for condition Aware-

262 NOGO/Unaware-GO, counterbalanced across participants according to the order depicted in Table 1.
 263 Each block consisted of 50 critical trials and 15 catch trials. The whole experiment was composed of
 264 48 blocks per participant, for a total of 2400 critical trials and 720 catch trials per participant. In order
 265 to test the experimental paradigm, we pilot-tested the task (see the Supplementary Materials section
 266 – Pilot Study).
 267

		Awareness	
		yes	no
Response	no	Aware-NOGO	Unaware-NOGO
	yes	Aware-GO	Unaware-GO

268 **Table 1. Experimental conditions.** Both Awareness and Response were manipulated: Awareness was
 269 experimentally manipulated by employing a threshold stimulus, so that sometimes it was consciously
 270 perceived (Aware) and sometimes not (Unaware). Response was manipulated by the task: in condition GO
 271 participants were asked to respond by pressing a key, while in condition NOGO they were asked to withhold
 272 responding. The combination of these two manipulations gives rise to the 4 experimental conditions depicted
 273 in the table.
 274

Participants	Day 1		Day 2	
	EROS montage 1	Task	EROS montage 2	Task
1	A	GNGG	B	NGGN
2	B	GNGG	A	NGGN
3	A	NGGN	B	GNGG
4	B	NGGN	A	GNGG

275 **Table 2. Counterbalancing of montages and task conditions across participants.** Both EROS montages
 276 and task conditions (G = Aware-GO/Unaware-NOGO; N = Aware-NOGO/Unaware-GO) were
 277 counterbalanced across participants. In the column “Task”, each letter represents 6 blocks of task. Thus, each
 278 day, participants performed 12 blocks per condition, for a total of 24 blocks of task per day.

279 2.6 Optical Recording

280 Three synchronized Imagent frequency domain systems (ISS, Inc., Champaign, IL) were used to
 281 record continuous fast optical data throughout experimental sessions. Each system was equipped with
 282 4 photo-multiplier tubes detectors, for a total of 12 detectors. Near-infrared light (830 nm) was
 283 delivered from 48 laser diodes on participants’ scalp and it was modulated at 110 MHz. Each of 12

284 detectors received light from sets of 16 light emitters, multiplexed every 25.6 ms, resulting in a
285 sampling rate of 39.0625 Hz.

286 To avoid cross-talk between channels, the array of source-detector pairs (i.e., the montage) was
287 created by means of a specific program (NOMAD, Near-Infrared Optode Montage Automated
288 Design) implemented in Matlab, useful to place sources and detectors at optimal distances. In this
289 experiment, we set the minimal distance to 17.5 mm and the maximum distance to 50 mm, in order
290 to ensure an extensive coverage of the brain regions of interest both from the spatial and the depth
291 point of view. The distance between the source and the detector of a channel, in fact, determines the
292 depth of the light pathway (Gratton *et al.*, 2000), thus corresponding to the depth of the investigation:
293 namely, longer channels can investigate deeper layers and shorter channels can examine shallower
294 regions.

295 Both light emitters and detectors were placed on participants head using a custom-built helmet. To
296 minimize interferences, before placing the optical fibers on the head, hairs were carefully moved with
297 cotton buds, so that the fibers could reach the scalp directly. In order to better adhere to the head of
298 the participant, we employed two helmets of different sizes: one 55-56 cm large, and one 57-58 cm
299 large. For each helmet, we developed two different montages, so that to provide a dense coverage of
300 the regions of interest (i.e., the left occipital, temporal and parietal cortices, see Figure 2). Each
301 montage consisted of the combination of 12 detectors and 48 light emitters, resulting in a total of 192
302 channels per montage. As mentioned before, each montage was recorded in a separate session, and
303 the order was counterbalanced across participants.

304 At the end of each EROS session, the scalp location of each source and detector was digitized in
305 relation to four fiducial points (i.e., nasion, inion and pre-auricular points) with a neuro-navigation
306 software (SofTaxis, E.M.S., Bologna, Italy) combined with a 3D optical digitizer (Polaris Vicra, NDI,
307 Waterloo, Canada). Afterwards, the digitized scalp locations were co-registered with each
308 participant's individual MRI, using a dedicated software package (OCP, Optimized Co-registration
309 Package, Matlab code developed by Chiarelli and colleagues (Chiarelli *et al.*, 2015).

310 For this reason, participants underwent a structural MRI at the Azienda Ospedaliera Universitaria
311 Integrata of Verona (AOUI).

312 **2.7 MRI Acquisition**

313 Participants' individual structural MRI was acquired by means of a 3 Tesla Philips Elition S scanner
314 with a 32-channel head RF receive coils. A whole brain high-resolution 3D T1-weighted image (T1w)
315 Turbo-field echo image (1mm-isotropic TE/TR=3.8/8.4 ms, TI=1050 ms) was acquired.

316 The T1w field of view (240 x 240 x 180 mm) was large enough to allow for the ears and the entire
317 scalp to be fully included in the image to facilitate later and accurate co-registration with functional
318 data.

319 **2.8 Data Analysis**

320 *2.8.1 Behavioral data*

321 Raw data were processed by means of custom scripts created on Matlab (the MathWorks, Inc., Natick,
322 MA). Data were divided into the 4 experimental conditions (i.e., Aware-GO, Unaware-NOGO,
323 Aware-NOGO, Unaware-GO). For each participant, trials with reaction times lower than 150 ms and
324 higher than 3 standard deviations from the mean were excluded from the analysis. Data were
325 successively analyzed using Jamovi (version 2.3.28): first, the percentage of Aware and Unaware
326 trials was calculated, in order to assess that a sufficient amount of trials was present for each
327 condition. Participants presenting more than 75% or less than 25% of Awareness were discarded from
328 the sample. This was because, in that case, the number of Unaware (or Aware) trials would be
329 insufficient for statistical EROS analysis. EROS technique, indeed, although having a high
330 localization power from both the spatial and temporal point of view, has a relatively low signal-to-
331 noise ratio. For this reason, a high number of trials is required for statistical analysis. Subsequently,
332 reaction times (RTs) were analyzed for the “GO” conditions, thus paired sample t-tests (two-tailed)
333 were applied to compare the mean RTs between Aware-GO and Unaware-GO conditions. Finally, to
334 verify that participants were performing the task accurately and that there were no biases related to
335 the response, catch trials were analyzed. As mentioned above, catch trials were those trials in which
336 all the radii of the stimulus were equally thick, thus no differences in the stimulus were present. In
337 case of catch trials, the participants’ task was different according to the condition: in the Aware-GO
338 condition, they were expected to withhold responding, while in the Aware-NOGO condition, they
339 were expected to respond. Thus, catch trials were analyzed separately for the two conditions (GO and
340 NOGO) by means of a paired sample t-test (two-tailed), in order to ensure that the behavioral
341 performance followed the above-mentioned trend. Paired sample t-tests (two-tailed) were indeed
342 performed to test whether catch trials performance was significantly different from critical trials.

343 *2.8.2 EROS data*

344 Pre-processing of continuous phase delay (i.e., time-of-flight) data was computed by means of a
345 dedicated in-house software, P-POD (Pre-Processing of Optical Data, run in Matlab, version
346 R2013b). Thus, raw data were normalized (i.e., corrected for phase wrapping and de-trended to
347 remove low-frequency drifts), demeaned and filtered by means of a 6th order Butterworth band-pass

348 filter which allows frequencies between 0.5 Hz and 15 Hz. Pulse artifacts were removed by using a
349 regression algorithm (GRATTON *et al.*, 1995). After that, data were averaged separately for each
350 subject, condition, and channel and segmented into epochs time-locked to the onset of the stimulus.
351 Each epoch comprised a period from 486 ms before the stimulus onset to 998 ms following the
352 stimulus onset, resulting in an epoch lasting 1484 ms. Subsequently, statistical analyses were
353 computed with an in-house software package (Opt-3d; (Gratton, 2000)), which provides statistical
354 spatial maps of fast optical data.

355 To perform statistics, data from channels whose diffusion paths intersect a given voxel were
356 combined (Wolf *et al.*, 2014). Phase delay data were spatially filtered with an 8-mm Gaussian kernel
357 and baseline corrected using a 204 ms time-window preceding the stimulus onset. Within each ROI,
358 t-Statistics were calculated at group level, converted into Z-scores and corrected for multiple
359 comparisons using random field theory (Worsley *et al.*, 1995; Kiebel *et al.*, 1999). Then, Z-scores
360 were weighted and orthogonally projected onto the surface of an MNI template brain, according to
361 the physical homogenous model (Arridge & Schweiger, 1995; Gratton, 2000).

362 In order to investigate the neural dynamics related to conscious vision and to disentangle the role of
363 the motor areas, the following contrasts between conditions were computed: 1) Aware-GO versus
364 Unaware-GO and 2) Aware-NOGO versus Unaware-NOGO. These contrasts allowed to investigate
365 the research questions the proposed study aimed at answering (see Section 3 for a detailed description
366 of the planned analysis). Importantly, both frequentist and Bayesian statistics (with default priors)
367 were computed, to test both positive and negative effects.

368 Moreover, Granger Causality analysis was computed. Granger Causality analysis allows to explore
369 the predictive interactions between different brain areas at different time-points. Specifically, this
370 approach requires a region of interest (ROI) to be used as a “seed” and investigating whether the
371 activity of this seed predicts activity in the other ROIs at a later time-lag, by deriving statistical maps
372 from t-statistics computation (then transformed into z scores) for each lag.

373 Statistical functional analysis was computed within specific predetermined regions of interest (ROIs)
374 and time intervals. ROIs were defined by a 2-dimensional box-shaped structure, covering an area of
375 20x20 millimeters. Critical ROIs were selected on the basis of the results obtained in the above-
376 mentioned experiment (Colombari *et al.*, 2024) and they were located in the occipital and in the left
377 parietal and temporal lobes, specifically over the primary visual cortex (V1, Brodmann Area 17), the
378 left lateral occipital cortex (LOC, Brodmann Area 19), the left supplementary motor area (SMA,
379 Brodmann Area 6), the left premotor area (PM, Brodmann Area 6) and the left primary motor cortex
380 (M1, Brodmann Area 4). Statistical analysis was computed within specific temporal windows of
381 interest selected on the basis of the results obtained by Colombari *et al.*, 2024. This is to reduce the

382 risk of false positives, as Opt3d does not offer the possibility to correct data for multiple comparisons
383 in the temporal domain. The specific time windows tested for each hypothesis are listed in Table 3.

384

385 **Figure 1. Trial procedure and stimuli:** A) Experimental procedure: the trial began with a fixation cross
386 persisting at the center of the screen for 500 ms. After that, an acoustic tone lasting 100 ms was presented,
387 followed by a random interval ranging from 500 to 600 ms. Then, the stimulus was presented for 100 ms and
388 participants were asked to respond according to the experimental condition (i.e., Aware GO or Aware-NOGO).

389 **B)** Example of stimuli: on the left is shown the catch stimulus, with all the radii equally thick; on the right is
390 depicted the critical stimulus, with the first radius, clockwise, thicker than the others.
391

392

393 **Figure 2. Covered area.** The gray area represents the area covered by the EROS montages (combined
394 together) from the sagittal, axial and coronal point of view.

3. Study design

Question	Hypothesis	Sampling Plan	Analysis Plan	Rationale for deciding the sensitivity of the test for confirming or disconfirming the hp	Interpretation given different outcomes	Observed Outcomes
<p>Q1: Can we replicate Colombari et al., 2024 findings showing that LOC is an NCC?</p>	<p>H1: We hypothesized to replicate Colombari et al., 2024 results: greater activity in LOC in an early temporal window (i.e., 150-350 ms post stimulus onset) is observed when contrasting Aware and Unaware trials in the condition in which the response is required (i.e., GO condition)</p> <p>Expected outcome:</p> <p>LOC aware-GO > LOC unaware-GO, as</p>	<p>Since the present research question aims at replicating the results of Colombari et al., 2024, sample size estimation is based on those EROS data. Sample size calculation was performed with G-Power software (v. 3.1.9.7), with a power of 90% and a significance level of 2%, resulting in 32 participants.</p>	<p>A1: The goal is to replicate the results of Colombari et al., 2024, in which the manual response was required for both Aware and Unaware conditions. Here, in order to perform the same analysis, early LOC activity in Aware-GO and Unaware-GO trials will was compared by using a paired-sample one-tailed t-test, computed with the EROS dedicated analysis software “Opt3d”.</p> <p>In addition to frequentist statistics, Bayesian statistics (with default prior) was computed to test potential null effects.</p> <p>Contrast to be computed:</p> <p>AWARE GO VS UNAWARE GO</p> <p>ROI to be tested:</p>	<p>Sample size estimation is based on previous EROS data (Colombari et al., 2024), on which similar analyses were performed.</p>	<p>O1.1: A significant t-test within the interval of interest is interpreted as a successful replication of previous findings, supporting the involvement of LOC in NCC.</p> <p>O1.2: The absence of this effect does not confirm the hypothesis, suggesting that LOC is not involved in the conscious detection of a stimulus property.</p>	<p>OO1: Our hypothesis was confirmed by our results, as the results from Colombari et al., was replicated. Indeed, when contrasting Aware and Unaware trials in the condition in which the response is required (i.e., GO condition), greater activity in LOC was observed 179 ms after the stimulus onset.</p>

	measured by EROS activity		LOC Time interval of interest: 150-350ms after stimulus onset			
Q2: Is the activity in LOC independent from the response?	<p>H2: We hypothesized that LOC activity is independent from response requirement: when contrasting activity elicited by Aware-NOGO trials with activity elicited by Unaware-NOGO trials, we expect to find the same activation of LOC found in the Aware-GO vs Unaware-GO contrast.</p> <p>Expected outcome:</p> <p>LOC aware-NOGO>LOC unaware-NOGO, as measured by EROS activity</p>	Since research question Q2 involves the same analyses of research question Q1 (but for the NOGO condition), the sampling plan for Q2 is the same as for Q1.	<p>A2.1: A paired-sample one-tailed t-test was computed in order to compare early activity in LOC in the NOGO condition. Thus, activity in Aware-NOGO and Unaware-NOGO trials will be was contrasted.</p> <p>Both frequentist and Bayesian statistics (with default prior) was computed.</p> <p>Contrast to be computed:</p> <p>AWARE NOGO VS UNAWARE NOGO</p> <p>ROI to be tested:</p> <p>LOC</p> <p>Time interval of interest:</p> <p>150-350ms after stimulus onset</p> <p>A2.2: The interaction effect between awareness and motor response was tested by means of a paired-sample one-tailed t-test computed between contrast Aware-GO VS Unaware-GO and contrast Aware-</p>	As above	<p>O2.1.1: A significant t-test in the time window of interest suggests that LOC activity is independent from response, since its activity is observed even when no response is required (NOGO conditions).</p> <p>O2.1.2: If greater activity in LOC in the time window of interest is not observed, then it means that LOC activity is somehow related to the motor response.</p> <p>O2.2.1: Significant interaction effect suggests that activity in LOC depends from response requirement</p> <p>O2.2.2: The absence of a difference between the two effects suggests that</p>	OO2: Our hypothesis was confirmed by our results, as greater activity in LOC was observed 204 ms after the presentation of the stimulus when contrasting activity elicited by Aware-NOGO trials with activity elicited by Unaware-NOGO trials, thus independently from response requirement.

	(LOC aware-GO>LOC unaware-GO)=(LOC aware-NOGO>LOC unaware-NOGO)		<p>NOGO VS Unaware-NOGO</p> <p>In addition to frequentist statistics, Bayesian statistics (with default prior) was computed to test potential null effects</p> <p>Contrast to be computed:</p> <p>(AWARE GO VS UNAWARE GO) - (AWARE NOGO VS UNAWARE NOGO)</p> <p>ROI to be tested:</p> <p>LOC</p> <p>Time interval of interest:</p> <p>150-350ms after stimulus onset</p>		motor response does not affect awareness-related activity in LOC	
Q3: Does consciousness modulate activation of motor areas in a detection task?	H3: When a motor response is required, consciousness modulates activation of motor areas (MA), as activity in motor areas is triggered by LOC (Colombari et al., 2024)	Considering that the estimated sample size for this study (n= 32) is more than twice the typical sample size of EROS studies present in literature (see Supplementary Table 1, where a systematic review of existing EROS literature revealing that the typical sample size used is 13 participants is depicted), the same estimated sample size of Q1 and	<p>A3.1 A paired-sample one-tailed t-test was computed in order to compare early activity in Motor Areas in the GO condition. Thus, activity in Aware-GO and Unaware-GO trials was contrasted.</p> <p>In addition to frequentist statistics, Bayesian statistics (with default prior) was computed to test potential null effects</p>	As above	<p>O3.1.1: A statistically significant difference between the two conditions suggests that, even in a detection task, response related motor activity is stronger in the Aware condition compared to the Unaware one.</p> <p>In Colombari et al., 2024 this difference was observed. Importantly, in this previous study a</p>	<p>OO3: Our hypothesis was partially supported by our results. Indeed, greater activity in M1 was observed when contrasting Aware and Unaware conditions, suggesting that response related motor activity is stronger in the Aware condition compared to the Unaware one</p> <p>However, Granger analysis revealed no</p>

	<p>Expected outcome:</p> <p>MA aware-GO>MA unaware-GO, as measured by EROS activity</p> <p>LOC activity predicts MA activity (investigated by means of Granger Causality Analysis)</p>	<p>Q2 seems to be also adequate to answer research questions Q3 and Q4.</p>	<p>Contrast to be computed:</p> <p>AWARE GO VS UNAWARE GO</p> <p>ROI to be tested:</p> <p>Motor areas</p> <p>Time interval of interest:</p> <p>Based on mean RTs, with a time window of ± 1.5 sd around the mean</p> <p>A3.2: In order to further investigate the flow of activity occurring in the investigated brain areas, Granger Causality Analysis was performed. In the present study, we performed Granger analysis on the “Aware-GO VS Unaware-GO” contrast, since we are interested in investigating whether activity in motor areas is predicted by previous activity in LOC, when a motor response is required (i.e., in the GO condition). Thus, LOC was used as seed ROI and later activity in motor areas was investigated.</p> <p>In addition to frequentist statistics, Bayesian statistics (with default</p>	<p><i>discrimination</i> task was employed and participants were asked to provide two different responses in case of Awareness (intentional) or Unawareness (random). Instead, in this study participants are asked to perform a <i>detection</i> task, in which the motor behavior made to provide the response, when required, is the same for both Aware and Unaware condition and thus no response selection is required.</p> <p>O3.1.2: If no difference between the tested conditions is observed, it will suggest that in a detection task there is no difference in the motor activity related to the response.</p> <p>O3.2.1: Significant predictive interactions between LOC and motor areas will suggest that, when the</p>	<p>significant predictive effects between extra-striate and motor areas.</p>
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			<p>prior) was computed to test potential null effects</p> <p>Contrast to be computed:</p> <p>AWARE GO VS UNAWARE GO</p> <p>ROI to be tested:</p> <p>LOC (as seed ROI) Motor areas as predicted areas</p> <p>Time interval of interest:</p> <p>LOC: 150-350 ms after the stimulus onset (within this interval, about ± 4 time points around the peak value -according to the peak waveform- were selected)</p> <p>MA: based on mean RTs, with a time window of ± 1.5 sd around the mean</p>	<p>stimulus enters consciousness, awareness-related activity in LOC predicts subsequent activity in motor areas. This (expected) outcome will suggest that consciousness modulates subsequent response-related motor activity, by directly triggering activation of motor areas, as observed in Colombari et al., 2024</p> <p>O3.2.2: If no significant interactions between LOC and MA will be highlighted, then it would mean that activity in motor areas is not predicted by LOC. Specifically, it could be surmised that in a <i>detection</i> task, consciousness does not modulate activation of motor areas, as observed in Colombari et al., 2024, where a <i>discrimination</i> task was employed. The difference in the two tasks, indeed, consists in the type of motor response required: in the case of the</p>	
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					<p>discrimination task, the participant is asked to press one button or another according to the response. Conversely, in a detection task, the participant has to press a key when the target stimulus is detected. Thus, no selection of the response is needed. This difference could play a role in the relationship between consciousness and motor areas.</p>	
<p>Q4: Does consciousness modulate activation of motor areas in ABSENCE of motor response?</p>	<p>H4: Consciousness modulates activation of motor areas, even if the motor response is not required</p> <p>Expected outcome:</p> <p>MA aware-NOGO>MA unaware-NOGO</p> <p>LOC predicts MA (investigated by means of Granger</p>	As Q3	<p>A4.1: A paired-sample one-tailed t-test was computed in order to compare activity in Motor Areas in the NOGO condition. Thus, activity in Aware-NOGO and Unaware-NOGO trials was contrasted.</p> <p>In addition to frequentist statistics, Bayesian statistics (with default prior) was computed to test potential null effects</p> <p>Contrast to be computed:</p> <p>AWARE NOGO VS UNAWARE NOGO</p> <p>ROI to be tested:</p> <p>Motor areas</p>	As above	<p>O4.1.1: A statistically significant t-test suggests that, when a motor response is not provided, the inhibition required to withhold responding is stronger when the visual characteristic of the stimulus is consciously perceived, compared to when no difference is perceived.</p> <p>O4.1.2: If no difference between the tested conditions is observed, this suggests that i) no inhibition is required to withhold</p>	<p>OO4: This hypothesis was not supported by our findings, as no significantly greater activation was observed in M1 when contrasting Aware and Unaware trials in the condition in which no motor response was required.</p>

	Causality Analysis)		<p>Time interval of interest: Based on mean RTs, with a time window of ± 1.5 sd around the mean</p> <p>A4.2: With the aim of investigating the flow of activity occurring in the investigated brain areas also in the condition where no response is required, Granger Analysis was performed on the “Aware-NOGO VS Unaware-NOGO” contrast. This allowed to investigate whether activity in motor areas is triggered by previous activity in LOC, even when a motor response is not required. Thus, LOC was used as seed ROI and later activity in motor areas was investigated.</p> <p>In addition to frequentist statistics, Bayesian statistics (with default prior) was computed to test potential null effects</p> <p>Contrast to be computed: AWARE NOGO VS UNAWARE NOGO</p> <p>ROI to be tested: LOC (as seed ROI)</p>		<p>responding, both in the Aware and Unaware condition, or ii) the inhibition is equally strong for the two conditions.</p> <p>O4.2.1: If significant predictive interactions between LOC and motor areas will be observed, then consciousness modulates subsequent activity in motor areas also in absence of a motor response. This could be due to inhibition of the response processes.</p> <p>O4.2.2: If no significant interactions between LOC and MA are highlighted, then LOC does not predict activity in motor areas in absence of motor response.</p>	
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			<p>Motor areas as predicted areas</p> <p>Time interval of interest: LOC: 150-350 ms after the stimulus onset (within this interval, about ± 4 time points around the peak value -according to the peak waveform- were selected)</p> <p>MA: Based on mean RTs, with a time window of ± 1.5 sd around the mean</p>			
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398 **5. Results**

399 *5.1 Behavioral Results*

400 Raw data were processed using scripts created on Matlab (version R2017b; the MathWorks, Inc.,
401 Natick, MA). Trials were sorted into the four experimental conditions (i.e., Aware-GO, Unaware-
402 NOGO, Aware-NOGO and Unaware-GO) based on the participants' responses. Aware trials were
403 those trials in which the participant reported perceiving the thicker radius, while Unaware trials were
404 those trials in which participants could not perceive that the radius was thicker.

405 As specified in Section 2.8 (Data Analysis), trials with RTs lower than 150 ms or higher than 3SD
406 from the mean were removed. After removal, we had on average 801.4 trials for the Aware-GO
407 condition, 372.7 for the Unaware-NOGO condition, 738.9 trials for the Aware-NOGO condition and
408 450.2 for the Unaware-GO. Thus, in the GO condition, Aware trials accounted for an average of
409 68.36% of the trials ($sd=9.64$), while in the NOGO condition, Aware trials accounted for 62.13% of
410 the trials ($sd=10.21$). A two-tailed paired-samples t-test comparing the number of Aware trials in the
411 GO and NOGO conditions revealed no statistically significant difference between conditions ($t(31) =$
412 $2.01, p = .053, \text{Cohen's } d = -.355$).

413 Subsequently, mean RTs for Aware and Unaware trials in the GO condition were calculated and
414 contrasted by means of a paired-sample two-tailed t-test. Statistical analysis highlighted that mean
415 RTs for the Aware condition (592.49.53 ms) and the Unaware condition (643.34 ms) were statistically
416 different ($t(31) = -4.19, p < .001, \text{Cohen's } d = -.741$).

417 Moreover, analysis of catch trials was performed as described in Section 2.8.1. As specified above,
418 catch trials were those in which all the stimulus radii were equally thick. Hence, in those cases,
419 participants should report not seeing the thicker radius. As expected, they correctly reported not
420 seeing the thicker radius on average 95.72% of the time ($sd=5.41$) in the Aware GO condition and
421 96.25% ($sd=5.10$) in the Aware NOGO condition. Paired sample (two-tailed) t-test revealed no
422 significant difference between the two conditions ($t(31) = -.63, p = .533, \text{Cohen's } d = -.11$).
423 Importantly, catch trials performance was significantly different from critical trials performance both
424 in the GO condition ($t(31) = -12.4, p < .001, \text{Cohen's } d = -2.19$) and in the NOGO condition ($t(31)$
425 $= -15.1, p < .001, \text{Cohen's } d = -2.66$).

426 *5.2 EROS Results*

427 EROS data were pre-processed with a dedicated in-house software, P-POD (Pre-Processing of Optical
428 Data, run in Matlab, version R2013b), as described in Section 2.8 and co-registered with each
429 subject's structural MRI using the dedicated OCP software package. Subsequently, we computed

430 statistical analyses on pre-processed data by means of the dedicated in-house software package Opt-
431 3d. EROS results are shown in Figure 3.

432 In order to address the research question Q1 (i.e., “Can we replicate Colombari et al., 2024 findings
433 showing that LOC is an NCC?”), we investigated awareness-related activity in LOC by comparing
434 Aware and Unaware trials in the condition in which the motor response was required. To do so,
435 Aware-GO and Unaware-GO conditions were contrasted, and activity in LOC was analyzed. EROS
436 analyses showed a significantly increased activation at 179 ms after the stimulus onset ($z = 2.80$; z
437 $\text{crit} = 2.47$).

438 In the same manner, with the aim of investigating whether the activity in LOC is independent from
439 the response (i.e., research question Q2) we contrasted Aware and Unaware trials in the condition
440 where the motor response was not required. Thus, the contrast between Aware-NOGO and Unaware-
441 NOGO conditions was computed, revealing that even when a motor response was not required, Aware
442 trials yielded greater activation in LOC 204 ms after stimulus onset. ($z = 3.37$; $z \text{ crit} = 2.75$).

443 Moreover, the interaction effect between awareness and motor response was tested by means of a
444 paired-sample one-tailed t-test comparing the contrast Aware-GO VS Unaware-GO and Aware-
445 NOGO VS Unaware-NOGO, and the interaction was not statistically significant. This null effect was
446 further confirmed by Bayesian statistics computed with the default prior. Specifically, the Bayes
447 factors indicated moderate support for the absence of an effect ($\text{BF}_{10} = 0.19$, error = 3.8%).

448 To address research questions Q3 and Q4, namely whether consciousness modulates activation of
449 motor areas both in the presence and absence of motor response, we investigated activity in the motor
450 areas while computing the above-mentioned contrasts. Indeed, the Aware-GO vs Unaware-GO
451 contrast showed that activity reached statistical significance in motor areas 511 ms after stimulus
452 onset ($z = 2.73$; $z \text{ crit} = 2.59$), whereas the contrast between aware and unaware trials in the NOGO
453 condition did not yield any significant results. To test this null effect, a Bayesian analysis using the
454 default prior was computed, providing moderate evidence against the effect ($\text{BF}_{10} = 0.20$, error =
455 3.7%).

456

457 **Figure 3. EROS results.** The upper panel shows the statistical parametric maps of the z-score difference
 458 computed contrasting Aware and Unaware trials in the GO condition. The lower panel shows the statistical
 459 parametric maps of the z-score difference computed by contrasting Aware and Unaware trials in the NOGO
 460 condition. Each map represents a 25.6 ms interval.

461 5.3 Granger Causality Analysis Results

462 To further investigate the flow of activity in the investigated brain areas, Granger causality analysis
 463 was performed. Specifically, since in research question Q3 we were interested in investigating
 464 whether activity in motor areas was predicted by previous activity in LOC when a motor response is
 465 required (i.e., in the GO condition), we performed Granger analysis on the “Aware-GO VS Unaware-
 466 GO” contrast using LOC as seed ROI and investigating later activity in motor areas.

467 This analysis revealed no significant predictive effects between extra-striate and motor areas.
 468 Importantly, Bayesian statistics computed with default priors confirmed the absence of an effect, as
 469 all confidence intervals included zero, further indicating that the estimated effects were not reliably
 470 different from the null hypothesis.

471 5. Discussion

472 The present study aimed to unravel the spatio-temporal dynamics underlying conscious vision by
 473 combining a go/no-go detection task with EROS recordings, thereby disentangling neural activity
 474 related to visual awareness from concurrent response-related mechanisms. Taken together, the results
 475 provide converging evidence for a central role of the LOC in conscious visual processing, while also
 476 shedding light on the relationship between awareness and motor activity.

477 As for research question Q1, the EROS data successfully replicated the main finding of Colombari et
478 al. (2024), showing greater activation in LOC approximately 179 ms after stimulus onset when
479 Aware-GO trials were contrasted with Unaware-GO trials. This early activation of LOC is consistent
480 with the temporal window of the ERP component most commonly associated with visual awareness,
481 the Visual Awareness Negativity (VAN; Koivisto & Revonsuo, 2010; Koivisto et al., 2016) and aligns
482 with previous MEG source localization evidence pointing to the lateral occipito-temporal region as a
483 key generator of awareness-related activity (Vanni et al., 1996; Liu et al., 2012). Source
484 reconstruction analyses of ERP data have consistently placed the VAN generators in the lateral
485 occipital and inferior occipito-temporal cortex (Ciupinska et al., 2025; Förster et al., 2020). These
486 findings fit within a broader theoretical and empirical framework, suggesting that the extra-striate
487 cortex, and in particular LOC, is a key area for the neural correlates of visual awareness (Rees et al.,
488 2002). Recent literature using different approaches, such as single-neuron recordings from the human
489 LOC across a variety of perceptual tasks (Quiroga et al., 2024) and a TMS-EROS paradigm bypassing
490 V1 feedforward input (Knight et al., 2024), has likewise identified LOC as a critical site of early
491 awareness-related activity, which is fully consistent with this picture. Importantly, the present result
492 extends beyond the discrimination paradigm employed by Colombari and colleagues, demonstrating
493 that the early involvement of LOC in conscious visual processing generalizes to a detection task in
494 which no selection between motor responses is required.

495 Crucially, the results for research question Q2 demonstrate that LOC activation at 204 ms post-
496 stimulus was equally present in the no-go condition, in which participants were asked to withhold
497 responding. The absence of significant interaction between awareness and response requirement,
498 further supported by Bayesian evidence in favor of the null hypothesis, confirms that the early LOC
499 response is not modulated by response requirements and therefore cannot be attributed to preparation
500 or execution of the motor response. This finding is consistent with the view put forward by Koivisto
501 et al. (2016), who argued that subjective visual awareness emerges prior to P3 and independently of
502 post-perceptual mechanisms. Along the same lines, Mazzi et al. (2020) demonstrated that the LP
503 component – but not the VAN – is modulated by the response criterion adopted by participants,
504 providing direct electrophysiological evidence that early posterior activity reflects the conscious
505 percept per se, whereas later components are contaminated by post-perceptual decision-related
506 processes. Taken together, these findings strongly argue for considering LOC early activity as a
507 genuine NCC rather than an epiphenomenon of response-related processes.

508 The finding that early LOC activation is independent of response requirement places the present
509 results in direct dialogue with a body of EEG and fMRI research aimed at dissociating genuine NCCs
510 from correlates of post-perceptual processing. No-report paradigms using EEG and fMRI have

511 consistently shown that the late positivity (LP), but not early posterior activity, is strongly modulated
512 by task demands, report requirements, and stimulus relevance (Schlossmacher et al., 2020; Dellert et
513 al., 2021; Hense et al., 2024; Kronemer et al., 2022). Specifically, Dellert et al. (2021) demonstrated,
514 using simultaneous EEG-fMRI, that awareness effects in LOC and in the early ERP component
515 (VAN) persisted across report and no-report conditions, whereas frontal awareness effects were
516 confined to the report condition. Likewise, Kronemer et al. (2022) identified awareness-related
517 activity in LOC across a broad network using a no-report fMRI masking paradigm, and Hense et al.
518 (2024) provided electrophysiological evidence for sustained conscious perception that similarly
519 implicated posterior rather than frontal cortex. The present EROS data, showing response-
520 independent LOC activation at approximately 200 ms, are fully consistent with this picture.
521 Moreover, the role played by attention in modulating early posterior awareness effects remains
522 debated. Several studies have reported that VAN amplitude is sensitive to both exogenous and
523 endogenous attentional manipulations (Koivisto et al., 2006; Bola & Doradzińska, 2021; Doradzińska
524 & Bola, 2024), and others have found that it can be dissociated from attentional effects (Cohen et al.,
525 2020; Dembski et al., 2021; Ciupińska et al., 2024). The present paradigm was not designed to
526 manipulate attention independently of awareness, and we therefore cannot rule out a contribution of
527 differential attentional engagement across aware and unaware trials. Importantly, however, the
528 response-independence of the LOC effect argues against the simplest confound, namely that LOC
529 activation merely reflects response-preparation processes triggered only in the aware condition. With
530 respect to the relevance of no-report paradigms more broadly, the findings from studies by Pitts et al.
531 (2014), Shafto & Pitts (2015), Schelonka et al. (2017), and Dellert et al. (2022) collectively establish
532 that late frontal and centro-parietal activity (including LP and P3) are particularly sensitive to task
533 relevance, response criterion, and attentional blink dynamics, while early occipito-temporal effects
534 show greater stability. This supports interpreting the early LOC effect reported here as more likely to
535 reflect the conscious percept per se, rather than a post-perceptual consequence of detecting the
536 stimulus and preparing a response.

537 Regarding research question Q3, the contrast between the aware and unaware conditions when a
538 motor response was required showed a significant increase in motor area activation at approximately
539 511 ms after stimulus onset, within a time window consistent with the mean reaction times observed
540 in the GO condition. This finding indicates that, even in a detection task in which the same motor
541 response is performed regardless of whether the stimulus is consciously perceived, awareness
542 modulates the magnitude of motor area activation. This result is consistent with Colombari et al.
543 (2024), who reported a similar effect in a discrimination task in which aware and unaware trials
544 required qualitatively different motor responses (i.e., a specific vs. a random button press), thus,

545 potentially introducing a response selection confound. By contrast, in the present detection task, the
546 motor output was identical across awareness levels, making it less likely that the observed difference
547 in motor area activity was driven by response selection demands alone, and suggesting that conscious
548 perception can modulate motor-related processing even in simple detection contexts. However,
549 another possible interpretation must be considered. Aware and Unaware trials differed not only in
550 awareness but also in mean reaction times, reflecting a well-established advantage in processing
551 speed for consciously perceived stimuli. In this respect, evidence accumulation frameworks propose
552 that neural signals in motor and centroparietal regions track a decision variable that builds to a
553 threshold, with its rate of rise scaling with the quality of sensory evidence (O'Connell et al., 2012;
554 Kelly & O'Connell, 2013; Twomey et al., 2015; Tagliabue et al., 2019). On this account, the greater
555 motor area activation at 511 ms in Aware-GO compared to Unaware-GO trials might reflect faster or
556 steeper accumulation in the aware condition, rather than awareness per se. We consider this
557 interpretation unlikely to fully account for the present result for two reasons. First, the motor
558 activation effect emerged at 511 ms, which falls within, rather than clearly before, the range of mean
559 RTs for both conditions; if the difference were driven by an earlier threshold crossing in the aware
560 condition, one might expect the effect to appear at a shorter latency. Second, in the present paradigm
561 the threshold stimulus was individually calibrated to produce approximately 50% detection: any
562 difference in evidence quality between aware and unaware trials is thus inherent to the phenomenal
563 state itself and cannot be independently manipulated without altering the experimental design.
564 Nonetheless, without a parametric manipulation of stimulus strength or a model-based analysis of the
565 RT distributions, we cannot definitively rule out the possibility that the motor area difference at 511
566 ms reflects, at least in part, a difference in the rate of decision accumulation between conditions.
567 Future work combining EROS with computational modelling of accumulation-to-bound dynamics
568 would help to disentangle these accounts. More generally, this interpretation is consistent with a
569 broader literature emphasizing that motor areas are sensitive not only to the execution of movements,
570 but also to the cognitive context in which they are embedded (Montani et al., 2026).

571 Addressing research question Q4, the analysis of the no-go condition revealed no significant
572 difference in motor area activity between aware and unaware trials, a null result further supported by
573 Bayesian evidence. This finding suggests that, when participants successfully withhold their motor
574 response, consciousness does not produce detectable differences in motor area activation, or,
575 alternatively, that any inhibitory activity elicited by conscious perception of the stimulus is equally
576 present across awareness levels and thus does not manifest as a difference in the contrast. This
577 interpretation aligns with the well-established role of the pre_SMA in response conflict resolution
578 and inhibitory motor control: meta-analytic evidence (Swick et al., 2008) consistently identifies the

579 pre-SMA as a region recruited across simple and complex go/no-go tasks, playing a critical role in
580 selecting appropriate behavior whether that entails executing or withholding a response. The absence
581 of a consciousness-related modulation of motor areas in the no-go condition thus suggests that the
582 inhibitory process required to withhold responding may operate at a level that is not differentially
583 sensitive to awareness in a detection context.

584 The investigation of the directed flow of activity between LOC and motor areas, using Granger
585 causality analyses, did not reveal significant predictive interactions between early LOC activation
586 and subsequent motor area dynamics, neither in the GO nor in the NO-GO condition. Although this
587 null result should be interpreted with caution, it was also supported by Bayesian evidence and, despite
588 being unexpected in light of Colombari et al. (2024)'s findings in a discrimination task, remains
589 informative and theoretically meaningful when considered alongside the pattern of results from the
590 conventional EROS analyses. Indeed, while awareness modulated motor area activation in the GO
591 condition, this modulation does not appear to be driven by a direct predictive influence of LOC on
592 motor areas. One possible interpretation is that the difference in task demands between the present
593 detection paradigm and the discrimination paradigm of Colombari et al. (2024) may account for this
594 discrepancy: in a discrimination task, the need to select among alternative responses may amplify the
595 predictive influence of awareness-related occipito-temporal activity on motor areas, a dynamic that
596 may be reduced or absent when only a single, stereotyped response is required. This interpretation is,
597 again, consistent with evidence showing that pre-SMA and premotor areas are particularly recruited
598 when response conflict or selection demands are high (Nachev et al., 2008; Rushworth et al., 2002),
599 and with the broader finding that the relationship between visual awareness and motor control is
600 flexible and contingent on the cognitive and biomechanical demands of the task (Montani et al.,
601 2026). A further, non-mutually exclusive, interpretation concerns the nature of the information that
602 LOC may need to convey to motor areas. In a discrimination task, LOC encodes specific perceptual
603 content (i.e., the orientation of the Gabor patch) that is directly relevant for selecting which response
604 to execute. On this account, the selection of the correct action to perform may depend on the
605 transmission of content-specific information to motor areas, and it is precisely this content-specific
606 process that the Granger causality analysis may have captured in Colombari et al. (2024). In a
607 detection task, by contrast, the motor system may not need access to detailed perceptual content, but
608 only to the presence of a target. This kind of signal can reach M1 through more generic sensorimotor
609 circuits, without requiring LOC to directly drive motor activity. From this perspective, the predictive
610 LOC–motor link may not reflect a general feature of awareness, but rather a process that becomes
611 relevant when the perceptual content encoded in LOC is necessary to guide response selection. This
612 interpretation is consistent with the present finding that LOC activation is equally present and equally

613 strong across GO and NOGO conditions, but its downstream influence on motor circuits depends on
614 whether that content is decision-relevant for the required action.

615 From a broader theoretical standpoint, the present findings speak to an ongoing debate in
616 consciousness research about the spatial and temporal locus of phenomenal awareness and its
617 relationship to cognition and action. The convergent evidence reviewed here – namely, early and
618 response-independent activation of LOC as a candidate NCC, the absence of a direct predictive link
619 from LOC to motor areas in a detection context, and the selective modulation of motor activity only
620 when a response is executed – seems to be better accommodated by a framework in which conscious
621 visual experience emerges from early, localized activity in extra-striate cortex, rather than depending
622 on late widespread activity. This interpretation is in line with converging report and no-report
623 evidence suggesting that later widespread activity mainly reflects post-perceptual processes such as
624 report, decision-making, and response selection, while the neural correlates of perceptual awareness
625 arise at earlier processing stages (Koivisto et al., 2016; Mazzi et al., 2020; Tsuchiya et al., 2015,
626 Mazzi et al., 2017). It is also consistent with the most recent large-scale adversarial test of the global
627 neuronal workspace theory and integrated information theory, in which decoding of conscious content
628 was strongest in posterior cortex and often unsuccessful in prefrontal areas (Cogitate Consortium et
629 al., 2025). However, an important qualification is necessary: the EROS montage employed here
630 covered occipital, temporal, and parietal cortices but did not extend to prefrontal cortex (see Figure 2
631 and the limitations paragraph below). The present data are therefore silent on whether prefrontal
632 activation accompanies the early LOC effect, and our conclusions should be read as characterizing
633 the temporal and spatial profile of awareness-related activity within the covered territory, not as
634 arbitrating the full frontal versus posterior NCC debate. Whether and when PFC activity constitutes
635 a genuine NCC or a post-perceptual correlate of report in paradigms such as the present one remains
636 an open question that EROS as currently configured cannot address.

637 Importantly, the comparison between the present study and Colombari et al. (2024) suggests that the
638 critical factor determining whether LOC drives motor areas is not awareness per se, but the degree to
639 which the specific perceptual content encoded in LOC is necessary to guide the required response.
640 This distinction between awareness as a presence signal and awareness as discriminative content may
641 prove a useful organizing principle for understanding when and how conscious perception propagates
642 to motor and executive areas and invite future work to systematically characterize the conditions
643 under which conscious perception shapes downstream processing.

644 The present findings should be interpreted in light of some limitations. First, although EROS provides
645 a valuable combination of temporal and spatial information, the montage used in the present study
646 did not provide full whole-brain coverage. In particular, major portions of the frontal cortex could not

647 be investigated because of the relatively limited number of available optodes. Therefore, the present
648 findings should not be interpreted as ruling out possible awareness-related activity in frontal areas,
649 which are considered crucial by some theories of consciousness (e.g., Dehaene and Changeux, 2011).
650 Importantly, our conclusions are restricted to the preregistered regions covered by the EROS
651 montage, namely posterior visual and motor-related areas.

652 Second, EROS has a relatively low signal-to-noise ratio compared with other neuroimaging
653 techniques and therefore requires a high number of trials to obtain reliable estimates. Although all
654 conditions retained a substantial number of trials after preprocessing, fewer trials were available in
655 the Unaware than in the Aware conditions. While this imbalance was anticipated and accounted for
656 in the preregistered exclusion criteria, this difference may have influenced signal quality to some
657 extent and should be considered when interpreting the results. Nonetheless, trial counts per condition
658 were well above the threshold for reliable EROS statistics, even for the less represented conditions.

659 Third, the in-house Opt-3d software implements correction for multiple comparisons in the spatial
660 domain but does not directly provide correction across the temporal domain. For this reason,
661 temporally extended effects should be interpreted with some caution. Importantly, however, this
662 concern is mitigated by the fact that all analyses were restricted to preregistered ROIs and time
663 windows. Future studies combining EROS with whole-brain EEG, MEG, or fMRI recordings may
664 help clarify how early LOC activity relates to later frontal and parietal dynamics during conscious
665 visual processing.

666 A further limitation concerns the interpretation of the motor-area effect observed at 511 ms in the
667 Aware-GO versus Unaware-GO contrast. Aware and Unaware trials differed not only in phenomenal
668 state but also in mean reaction time, with responses being faster in Aware trials than in Unaware trials
669 (592 ms vs. 643 ms, respectively). This difference is unlikely to reflect differences in stimulus quality,
670 since the same threshold stimulus was used across all trials. Rather, it plausibly reflects the
671 phenomenological difference between responding on the basis of a conscious percept and responding
672 in its absence, with the latter condition introducing greater decisional uncertainty and a less direct
673 mapping between sensory input and motor output. To this extent, the RT difference may itself be a
674 consequence of the awareness manipulation rather than an independent confound. Future studies
675 combining EROS with computational modelling of decision accumulation would help to fully
676 characterize the relationship between conscious state, response speed, and motor-area activation in
677 paradigms of this type.

678 In conclusion, the present registered report provides robust and pre-registered evidence that LOC
679 represents a key extra-striate correlate of visual awareness, whose activity appears to be independent
680 of motor response requirements. Moreover, by demonstrating that awareness selectively modulates

681 motor area activation only when a response is executed, the study helps clarify the nature of the
682 interplay between awareness-related extra-striate regions and response-related motor areas, thereby
683 advancing our understanding of the neural architecture underlying the early genesis of phenomenal
684 awareness and the conditions under which conscious perception shapes downstream motor activity.

685 **Data availability**

686 Raw and processed anonymized data, as well as study materials, are publicly available as open data
687 at this link: https://osf.io/ebfu3/?view_only=9ec2e6bf32ba4a8bb8b858639ec40a59

688 **Code availability**

689 All analysis codes are publicly available as open data at this link:
690 https://osf.io/ebfu3/?view_only=9ec2e6bf32ba4a8bb8b858639ec40a59.

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702 **Author contributions**

703 **EC** Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data
704 Curation, Writing - Original Draft, Visualization, Funding Acquisition; **GP** Methodology, Formal
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706 Writing - Review & Editing **CM** Methodology, Software, Data Curation, Writing - Review & Editing,
707 Supervision; **SS** Conceptualization, Methodology, Resources, Writing - Review & Editing,
708 Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

709 **Competing interests**

710 The authors declare no competing interests.

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900 **Supplementary Figure S1. ROI analysis results obtained contrasting Aware and Unaware conditions.**
 901 Optical signal was averaged across all voxels within the predefined regions of interest (LOC and MA). In all
 902 panels, the blue trace represents the average waveform across all voxels obtained by contrasting trials from
 903 the Aware condition with those from the Unaware condition. The box plots summarize the contrast values at
 904 the significant time point (highlighted with the red circle in the waveform), with overlaid dots representing
 905 individual data

Title	Authors	Journal	Year of publication	Sample size
Shades of gray matter: Noninvasive optical images of human brain responses during visual stimulation	Gratton, G., Corballis, P.M., Cho, E., Fabiani, M., & Hood, D.C.	Psychophysiology	1995	3
Fast and Localized Event-Related Optical Signals (EROS) in the Human Occipital Cortex: Comparisons with the Visual Evoked Potential and fMRI	Gratton, G., Fabiani, M., Corballis, P.M., Hood, D.C., Goodman-Wood, M.R., Hirsch, J., Kim, K., Friedman, D., & Gratton, E.	Neuroimage	1997	3
Toward noninvasive 3-D imaging of the time course of cortical activity: Investigation of the depth of the Event-Related Optical Signal	Gratton, G., Sarno, A., Maclin, E., Corballis, P.M., and Fabiani, M.	Neuroimage	2000	9
Comparison of Neuronal and Hemodynamic Measures of the Brain Response to Visual Stimulation: An Optical Imaging Study	Gratton, G., Goodman-Wood, M.R., & Fabiani, M.	Human Brain Mapping	2001	8
The event-related optical signal (EROS) in visual cortex: Replicability, consistency, localization, and resolution	Gratton, G. & Fabiani, M.	Psychophysiology	2003	8
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			mean	12.944
			SD	7.008

907 **Pilot study**

908 In order to test the experimental paradigm, we pilot-tested the task.

909 A total of 10 right-handed participants (5 females and 5 males; mean age \pm standard deviation: 21
910 years \pm 1.0) took part in the pilot study. They all reported normal or corrected-to-normal vision and
911 no history of neurological or psychiatric disorders. All of them provided written informed consent
912 before starting the experiment.

913 After the first session, two participants dropped out the experiment, hence data from 8 participants
914 were included in the statistical analyses. Moreover, in order to maintain an equal number of trials in
915 both the conditions (i.e., Aware and Unaware), the percentage of Aware and Unaware trials was
916 calculated and data from participants reporting a proportion of awareness equal or superior to 80%
917 (i.e., 3 participants) were discarded from subsequent analysis. For this pilot study, we decided to raise
918 the awareness threshold of acceptance to 80% (instead of 75%, that will be used in the experiment)
919 in order to be more inclusive, given the low number of participants.

920 Thus, in total, data from 5 participants were included in the behavioral and functional analyses.

921 **Preliminary Results**

922 *Behavioral results*

923 Raw data were processed by means of scripts created on Matlab (version R2017b; the MathWorks,
924 Inc., Natick, MA). According to the participants' responses, trials were sorted into the four
925 experimental conditions (i.e., Aware-GO, Unaware-NOGO, Aware-NOGO and Unaware-GO).
926 Aware trials were those trials in which the participant reported to perceive the thicker radius, while
927 Unaware trials were those trials in which participants could not perceive that the radius was thicker.
928 As specified in Section 2.8, trials with RTs lower than 150 ms or higher than 3SD from the mean
929 were removed. After removal, we had on average 830.6 trials for the Aware-GO condition, 389.2 for
930 the Unaware-NOGO condition, 738.8 trials for the Aware-NOGO condition and 491.4 for the
931 Unaware-GO.

932 Subsequently, once assessed the normality of RTs and Awareness distributions (Shapiro-Wilk test.
933 RTs distribution: $W=0.824$, $p=0.125$; Awareness distribution: $W=0.817$, $p=0.112$), the percentage of
934 Awareness for the two conditions was calculated: in the GO condition, Aware trials represented on
935 average 68.02% of the trials, while in the NOGO condition, Aware trials constituted the 59.82% of
936 the trials. Paired sample (two-tailed) t-test performed with Jamovi (version 2.3.28) highlighted that
937 there was no significant difference between the two conditions ($t_{(4)} = 1.88$, $p = .134$, Cohen's $d =$
938 $.839$). Similarly, mean RTs for Aware and Unaware trials in the GO condition were contrasted and
939 the statistical analysis (Paired sample two-tailed t-test) revealed that mean RTs for the Aware

940 condition (628.530 ms) and the Unaware condition (675.317 ms) were not statistically different ($t(4)$
941 $= -1.77$, $p = .152$, Cohen's $d = -.791$). The behavioral results are depicted in Figure 3.
942 Moreover, in order to verify that the employed paradigm works as planned and that participants
943 performed the task accurately, analysis on catch trials was performed as described in Section 2.8.1
944 *Behavioral data*. As specified above, catch trials were those trials in which all the radii of the stimulus
945 are equally thick. Hence, in those cases, participants should report not to see the thicker radius. As
946 expected, they correctly reported not seeing the thicker radius on average the 96.47% of times
947 ($sd=2.49$) in the Aware GO condition and the 98.36% ($sd=1.89$) in the Aware NOGO condition.
948 Paired sample (two-tailed) t-test revealed no significant difference between the two conditions.
949

950
951 **Figure 3. Behavioral results.** The percentage of Awareness was calculated for both “GO” and “NOGO”
952 conditions (on the left). Mean reaction times were calculated for Aware and Unaware trials only for the “GO”
953 condition (on the right). No significant differences were observed. Error bars represent SEM and gray dots
954 represent individual data points showing the data distribution.

955 *EROS results*

956 EROS data were pre-processed with a dedicated in-house software, P-POD (Pre-Processing of Optical
957 Data, run in Matlab, version R2013b), as described in Section 2.8. Subsequently, we computed
958 statistical analyses on pre-processed data by means of the dedicated in-house software package Opt-
959 3d.

960 For this pilot study, participants' individual structural MR images could not be acquired, so an
961 estimated MR-based head model was individually created using the Softaxic Optic system (Softaxic,
962 E.M.S., Bologna, Italy) combined with a 3D optical digitizer (Polaris Vicra, NDI, Waterloo, Canada).
963 EROS data were thus co-registered with the estimated MRI using a specific procedure performed in
964 OCP software package (as specified above). Finally, co-registered data were transformed into MNI
965 space for subsequent analyses.

966 For both GO and NOGO conditions, Aware and Unaware trials were contrasted. As shown in Figure
967 4, the Aware-GO vs Unaware-GO contrast replicated the results obtained by Colombari et al., 2024.

968 In this contrast, indeed, we compared conditions in which the motor response was required, thus
 969 replicating the task carried out in the previously mentioned experiment. Also in this case, Aware trials
 970 elicited a sustained activation of LOC (230 and 332 ms after the stimulus onset), followed by the
 971 recurrent activation of the primary visual cortex (V1) and the motor areas (MA) at later stages of
 972 stimulus processing.
 973 Similarly, contrasting Aware and Unaware trials in the condition where the motor response was not
 974 required (i.e., the NOGO condition), greater activation of LOC was elicited in a timing comparable
 975 to that of the contrast just mentioned above (i.e., 307 ms after the stimulus presentation). Interestingly,
 976 also in this case awareness-related processing elicited activity in the motor areas, 563 ms after the
 977 stimulus onset, despite in this condition no response was required, possibly suggesting an inhibition
 978 to respond for the NOGO trials.

979 **Figure 4. EROS results.** Statistical parametric maps of the z-score difference computed contrasting Aware
 980 and Unaware trials in the GO (upper panel) and NOGO condition (lower panel). Each map represents a 25.6
 981 ms interval.
 982

983 Preliminary Discussion

984 The aim of the present pilot study was to assess whether the task and the experimental procedure were
 985 suitable to investigate the study's research questions.

986 As described in Section 4.1, the pilot study successfully replicated the trend of activations observed
 987 by Colombari et al., 2024, suggesting that the proposed study proves to be feasible in terms of
 988 methodology. For the sake of clarity, it is important to point out that the preliminary results reported
 989 here do not reach the statistical level of significance. This outcome was expected as data from only 5
 990 participants were included in the analysis. For the same reason, we decided not to perform Granger
 991 Causality analysis as for this kind of analysis results from 5 participants would have been

992 uninformative. Nevertheless, it was possible to observe that the proposed task could elicit a pattern
993 of activation similar to that observed by Colombari et al., 2024, suggesting that the experimental
994 paradigm proposed to investigate the research questions is suitable.